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MS # 16567 - From Bride to Candidate at 18: Aligning Electoral Eligibility with Marriage Eligibility in Japan

Ryuhei Ishibashi
Department of Gender and Social Policy
Elanare Institute
Tokyo, Japan

Dear Prof. Ishibashi:

Thank you for submitting your manuscript to *Gender & Society*. Unfortunately, *Gender & Society* is not the most appropriate place for it, and we are not sending the paper out for external review. To put this decision into context, *Gender & Society* receives more than 900 papers a year and publishes fewer than 3% of these submissions.

Articles in *Gender & Society* follow a fairly consistent format (see the journal's Guide for New Submissions, or a recent issue of the journal). Ours is a sociology journal. We seek to publish articles that expand sociological theories on gender or make original contributions to empirical scholarship of interest to sociologists of gender.

If you wish to submit to *Gender & Society* in the future, attached is a document with submission guidelines.

Thank you for your interest in *Gender & Society*. We send our best wishes for success in your ongoing work.

Sincerely,

Gender & Society Editorial team
gendersociety@socwomen.org

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